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European Maturity Model for Blended Education⁺

Backgrounds and the draft model

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0. Background

This document introduces the new European Maturity Model for Blended Education, developed through the EMBED+ initiative to support higher education institutions (HEIs) in enhancing their blended practices. Building on the original EMBED project, the model has been updated, upgraded and refined based on evidence from use case assessments, a systematic review of studies, and additional insights presented throughout this document. This ensures that the model is both practically relevant and grounded in research, providing institutions with clear guidance for improving blended education across diverse European contexts.

By translating evidence into actionable recommendations, the model offers maturity levels, dimensions and indicators, which give way to pathways and practical tools that can guide HEIs in their strategic planning. At the same time, it aligns with broader European digital education goals, fostering professional development, transnational collaboration, and equitable access to high-quality blended teaching and learning (BT&L). In this way, the model serves as both a diagnostic tool and a roadmap for advancing institutional capacity and Europe's leadership in digital education.

1. About blended learning environments

1.1. Concepts and container terms

The terminology surrounding blended learning (BL), blended teaching (BT), and blended education (BE) lacks consistent usage across the literature (Garrison & Vaughan, 2008; Sloman, 2007). Various definitions have been proposed to encapsulate the concept of BL. For instance, Yuan, Li, and Zhang (2014) describe it as a "combined teaching in many forms" (p. 5745), while Baehr (2012) characterizes it as a form of learning that utilizes "a combination of multiple media types, technologies, and communication modes" (p. 175). Hew and Cheung (2014) define BL as "any time a student learns at least in part at a supervised brick-and-mortar location away from home and at least in part through the Internet with some element of student control over time, place, and/or pace" (p. 2). Across more contemporary studies, the concept consistently emphasizes the integration of traditional face-to-face with online activities (Salmon, 2021; Versmissen et al., 2022). This dual-mode approach is not merely additive; rather, it represents a deliberate combination of modalities to enhance pedagogical effectiveness (Janse van Rensburg & Oguttu, 2022). Boelens et al. (2015) define it as "a deliberate combination of online and classroom-based interventions to instigate and support learning." Similarly, Vernadakis et al. (2011) refer to blended learning as "a new course delivery style (...) that combined the best features of online learning and traditional classroom learning." Angawi and Tasir (2024) note: "Blended learning strives to harmonize traditional teaching methods with online resources to optimize educational outcomes across diverse disciplines." In the same vein, Ma and Lee (2021) emphasize the integrative dimension of blended learning as an approach that seeks to "integrate benefits afforded by both traditional face-to-face learning and pure online learning to deliver course content." Singh et al. (2021) extend this view by framing blended learning as "an instructional method that includes the efficiency and socialization opportunities of the traditional face-to-face classroom with the digitally enhanced learning possibilities of the online mode of delivery." The blended format aims to maintain coherence across learning activities, ensuring that online and face-to-face components are complementary rather than disjointed (Amenduni & Ligorio, 2022; Istenič, 2024).

Taken together, these definitions highlight that blended learning – as well as is blended teaching – is not a singular or uniform concept, but rather a container term encompassing a range of practices that combine physical and virtual learning environments. Moreover, a distinction between the instructional and learning perspectives – two sides of the same coin – need to be distinguished. As Lowyck (1995, p. 216) defines it, teaching is "an educational activity aimed at triggering learning processes in students." *Instruction* involves the intentional design and facilitation of learning experiences, while *learning* represents the active, often self-regulated process through which students engage with and make meaning from these experiences. At its core, blended teaching and learning (BT&L) involve a purposeful integration of multimodal formats, aiming to harness the pedagogical strengths of both. However, as Hrastinski (2019) notes, the concepts have been used so broadly that they can refer to almost any form of learning and teaching. Therefore, it is crucial that researchers and practitioners explicitly define what the used concepts means in their specific contexts,

defined by three questions, namely “What, how and why are we blending?”. This clarity is essential not only for empirical research but also for the design and evaluation of educational practices.

1.2. Characteristics of blended learning environments

1.2.1. Digital technology integration versus blended teaching and learning

Rather than positioning technology as an external aid - as is common in discussions of *technology integration* - blended learning environments conceptualize technology as the connective tissue linking differently formatted educational activities. Technology enables collaboration and interaction across modalities and supports flexibility in pace, place, path, and time, thereby granting educators and learners greater control over teaching and learning (T&L) processes. It also extends student engagement beyond physical boundaries and allows educators to repurpose and optimize classroom time. Ultimately, blended learning cultivates a dual presence, combining face-to-face and computer-mediated interactions in ways that reshape traditional constraints of education.

Blended learning centres on the learner’s experience of seamlessly integrated processes across modalities, whereas blended teaching focuses on the educator’s design and facilitation of those processes, both grounded in intentional integration. In blended settings, the role of the educational expert is to deliberately orchestrate instructional activities that initiate and guide learners’ meaning-making. Importantly, this function need not be performed exclusively by human educators; information systems (IS) can also assume teaching roles by providing instruction, adaptive feedback, guidance, and assessment.

This orchestration involves carefully planning the proportion and sequencing of online and face-to-face components to create pedagogical coherence. As Kerres and De Witt (2003) argue, effective blended learning requires designing instructional “arrangements” that align content, communication, and media within an integrated didactical framework. Accordingly, educators, instructional designers, or IS act as mediators who match the affordances of digital media and technologies with specific pedagogical intentions.

1.2.2. Integration of virtual and physical learning environments

The concept of integration lies at the core of BT&L. It represents the meaningful combination of activities into a coherent whole. It involves synchronous and asynchronous communication and interaction in virtual and physical learning spaces.

- On one end of the continuum, onsite learning activities involve both analogue and digital learning resources that are not connected to the internet - for example, textbooks, printed materials, or locally stored digital files. These activities support face-to-face learning without connectivity.
- On the other end, online learning activities rely on internet-based resources such as intranets, extranets, or open web environments. These activities are characterized by digital learning resources with connectivity, enabling communication, collaboration, and access to dynamic information networks.

The focus is not merely on alternating between environments, but on creating a seamless, interconnected learning experience where both components complement and reinforce each other.

1.2.3. Proportion and sequencing of online and F2F educational activities

Two additional essential design characteristics in BLEs are *proportion* and *sequencing*, which together determine how online and face-to-face components are balanced and interconnected within a course or learning trajectory.

Proportion and sequencing form the structural backbone of blended learning designs. *Proportion* refers to the relative weight or balance between face-to-face and online learning activities. This balance may vary widely depending on pedagogical goals, learner characteristics, and contextual factors such as time, infrastructure, or subject matter.

In some cases, face-to-face learning may dominate, for example, when in-person interaction or hands-on practice is central to achieving learning outcomes. In other designs, online components may take precedence, especially when flexibility, accessibility, or individualized learning pathways are prioritized. Rather than seeking a fixed ratio, proportion in blended learning should be understood as a context-sensitive design choice, aimed at optimizing engagement, interaction, and learning effectiveness. *Sequencing*, by contrast, concerns the order and connection of learning activities across modalities. It determines how face-to-face and online experiences are organized over time to create pedagogical coherence.

Three main sequencing patterns can be distinguished:

1. *Preparation (e.g. flipped classroom)*: face-to-face and online learning activities are designed to serve different but complementary purposes. Typically, face-to-face activities prepare learners for online engagement (or vice versa). This is a common sequencing in flipped classrooms, whereby students engage in preparatory activities aimed at orientation and at building a foundational knowledge base. During the contact session, instructional time is dedicated to reproductive and/or productive knowledge development. For example, students might complete an individual diagnostic test or reading task face-to-face before participating in collaborative online group work. This sequencing enhances readiness and ensures that online participation builds upon prior knowledge or reflection.
2. *Replication (e.g. practice and reinforcement)*: occurs when similar types of learning activities are carried out in both face-to-face and online formats. For instance, learners might solve practice exercises in class and then repeat the same kind of activity in an online environment. This approach can strengthen retention, offer additional practice opportunities, and provide varied forms of feedback across modalities.
3. *Extension (e.g. solving complex tasks)*: involves complementary face-to-face and online activities that expand or deepen learning. Learners engage in tasks that build upon each other across environments - for example, consulting a textbook while solving an online case study or applying theory learned in class to an online simulation. Or, after establishing the knowledge base and engaging in guided practice during face-to-face sessions, students proceed in groups to tackle problem-based tasks online.

Together, these types provide educators, instructional designers or instructional design teams with a conceptual framework for analysing and creating their instructional approaches.

Blended T&L practices can be further understood through three interrelated, key dimensions: *interaction, communication and regulation* (or control). In essence it is not merely about combining online and F2F modalities but about orchestrating activities/experiences across spaces, actors, and media. Understanding and deliberately designing along these dimensions enables one to create more effective T&L experiences.

1.2.4. Interaction across multiple spatial and relational planes

Interaction lies at the heart of BT&L in BLEs and occurs across multiple spatial and relational planes.

1. In terms of *place*, interactions can take place face-to-face (in physical classrooms) or at a distance (in virtual or online spaces), often blending both within a single learning sequence.
2. Different *actors* participate in these interactions:
 - Learner-educator interactions, which focus on guidance, scaffolding, and feedback.
 - Learner-learner interactions, which promote collaboration, peer learning, and social presence.
 - Learner-information system interactions, which involve engagement with digital tools or technologies.
3. *Feedback* within these interactions can vary from non-adaptive (standardized or static) to adaptive (personalized and responsive), depending on whether it is provided by a human source (educator or peer) or an information system that dynamically responds to learner input.

1.2.5. Communication along two main subdimensions: time and symmetry

Communication in BLEs is defined along two main subdimensions. These affect the flow of information, the sense of community, and the degree of learner participation within blended environments.

1. The *temporal dimension* distinguishes between synchronous communication (real-time exchanges such as live video sessions or in-class discussions) and asynchronous communication, which allows learners to engage at different times (e.g., discussion forums, recorded lectures, annotated feedback)
2. The *symmetry dimension* refers to the direction and balance of communication:
 - One-to-many (e.g., educator delivering content to a group),
 - Many-to-many (e.g., group collaboration or peer discussion), and
 - One-on-one (e.g., individualized tutoring or mentoring).

1.2.6. Control of learning path and learner pace

The control dimension concerns who directs learning process. It can be analysed across two aspects: path and pace. The learning path may be determined primarily by the educator or information system, by the learner or class, or shared between both. Similarly, the learning pace, how quickly learners progress through blended learning activities can range from educator-paced or system-paced to self-paced models that allow learners to advance according to their needs and goals.

1.3. EMBED+: Preliminaries and common denominators

In the EMBED project, learning is conceptualized as a process through which learners develop adaptive competence by engaging in constructive, self-regulated, situated, and collaborative activities, whether formal or informal (adapted from De Corte, 2010). Central to any learning environment is its pedagogical core, defined as the “setting and natural environment in which teaching and learning occur” (Hew & Cheung, 2014, p. 111). In higher education, this core comprises four interrelated elements (OECD, 2018): (1) learners (who engages in learning?), (2) educators (with whom do learners interact?), (3) content (what is learned?), and (4) resources (with what means or tools?). *A blended learning environment (BLE) builds on this framework by deliberately combining face-to-face T&L interactions and physical tools with T&L interactions and computer-mediated tools in virtual spaces.* In BLEs, design ensures that online and face-to-face components are integrated, purposeful, and complementary, supporting (the orchestration of) learning across modalities.

Closely related concepts are *hybrid learning* and *hybrid teaching*, which refer to a *synchronous combination of virtual and physical learning spaces*. For instance, a hybrid learning scenario may involve students simultaneously engaging with printed materials and online resources, while hybrid teaching may take place when an educator interacts concurrently with students in a physical classroom and those connected remotely via videoconference.

1.3.1. Defining the blend

In the context of EMBED the following definitions are used for describing Blended Learning (BL), Blended Teaching (BT), and Blended education:

Blended learning is defined as learning resulting from an integrated combination of online and face-to-face learning activities.

Blended learning refers to the learner’s experience of integrating online and face-to-face activities into a coherent learning process. In EMBED, blended learning is not simply the presence of multiple modalities; it is the purposeful and meaningful combination of synchronous and asynchronous interactions across physical and digital spaces. The focus lies on how students experience and navigate integrated, flexible learning paths combining pace, place, path, and time. Blended learning therefore represents the outcome of instructional design that supports connected learning activities, and continuity across learning environments.

Blended teaching refers to designing and facilitating blended learning activities.

Blended teaching refers to the educator's design, orchestration, and facilitation of blended learning activities. Educators deliberately combine online and face-to-face components to instigate and support learning processes, aligning learning outcomes, teaching activities, interactions, media, and assessment strategies. EMBED views blended teaching as a pedagogically driven process in which educators create coherent learning arrangements that leverage the affordances of both digital and physical environments. This also includes facilitation roles - guiding students, offering feedback, ensuring presence across modalities, and coordinating learning sequences. These responsibilities may be supported or complemented by information systems but remain grounded in purposeful instructional design.

Blended education is the formal context in which blended teaching and blended learning take place, determined by policies and conditions with regard to the organization and support of blended teaching and learning.

Blended education represents the organisational and programmatic context within which blended teaching and blended learning occur. Whereas blended learning operates at the student level and blended teaching at the course level, blended education concerns the systemic embedding of blended approaches across programmes and the organisation. According to EMBED, blended education is shaped by policies, quality assurance, support structures, professional development, organisational strategy, and digital-physical infrastructure. It ensures that blended teaching and learning are sustainable, scalable, and coherently supported across courses and departments. In this sense, blended education is the formal context that determines how blended learning and teaching can be effectively enacted.

Together, these three concepts form a layered model (see also Van Valkenburg et al., 2020; Goeman et al., 2021; Goeman & Dijkstra, 2025):

1. *Blended learning*: the learner experience of integrated online and face-to-face activities.
2. *Blended teaching*: the educator's design and facilitation of those integrated activities.
3. *Blended education*: the organisational framework enabling and supporting blended practices at scale.

EMBED emphasizes that high-quality blended education requires coherence among all three layers, grounded in intentionality, alignment, sustainability, and support.

1.3.2. The constructive alignment

EMBED assumes that educators or instructional designers are knowledgeable about how to align course objectives or expected outcomes with target student groups, learning activities and assessment (both formative and summative). Constructive alignment (Biggs & Tang, 2007) is considered the basis for course and programme design and EMBED also considers this the basis for blended course and programme design.

1.3.3. The value of (informed) design

EMBED explicitly adheres to a design-focused approach of courses and programmes. Consequently, growth in maturity is considered as a result of the ability of (teams of) instructors, instructional designers and others involved, to make informed decisions. This includes using design principles and/or instructional theories, from blended course design right up to whole programme design, that is the organisation, planning and documentation of a structured series of courses or units).

1.4. Design of blended learning environments

1.4.1. From pedagogical foundations to design principles

Where pedagogical principles address the question, “What kind of learning and teaching do we value?” - reflecting underlying values, aims, and learning theories - design principles answer the question, “How should we construct the environment to realize those values?” - providing practical, actionable guidance derived from both theory and design practice.

A design principle is a normative, actionable guideline derived from research and iterative design practice, often through design-based research, that specifies how to structure a learning environment to achieve particular pedagogical goals.

In the design-based research literature, design principles are regarded as the tangible outcomes of iterative design work: they outline the features of effective learning environments and provide guidance for the design of future educational interventions, effectively translating pedagogical aims into concrete, designable elements (van den Berg & Bozalek, 2024). For example, one recent study notes that the design principles developed were intended “to guide the design of hybrid STEM learning environments”. The authors first develop a pedagogical framework (personalization of learning, learner-centredness, connections to prior experience, versatility in novel and conventional tools and methods, etc.). Subsequently, they derive concrete design principles for the learning environment from that framework, such as: organise dialogues, consider learner profiles, use multiple tools that guide how to build the blended learning environment (Mäkelä et al., 2022).

Where pedagogical principles articulate what kind of learning and teaching is valued, design principles for BLEs specify how these values can be enacted across and through modes. What is unique to BLEs in terms of design principles? Blended learning environments occupy a distinctive position in educational design because they intentionally integrate physical and digital learning spaces, synchronously and asynchronously, to achieve constructive alignment (course level) or curriculum coherence (programme level) and flexibility (course and programme level). Kerres and De Witt's highly cited article of 2003 outlines three critical didactical components which specify BL “arrangements”: (1) content, (2) communication, (3) construction. An educator selects beforehand a particular combination of these components in its course design (proportioning and sequencing), their respective delivery mode (online or face-to-face), and the extent of cooperation for (individual or group-based) and their order.

1.4.2. What makes blended approaches distinct?

The 'DNA' of a BT practice can be represented by a unique string of particularly sequenced online and face-to-face learning activities, defined by the task character (content, communication, construction) and their grouping (Bocconi & Trentin, 2014). As such, design principles must not only address issues regarding time, space, pace and path, but also the interaction and alignment between multiple modalities and tools. This requires principles that guide the orchestration of activities, technologies, and social interactions so that learning remains continuous, inclusive, and pedagogically coherent across contexts.

For blended learning environments, therefore, design principles uniquely:

- *Address the orchestration of modalities and spaces:* principles guide how to distribute learning activities meaningfully between online and face-to-face components (e.g., constructive alignment between in-class discussion and online reflection). They ensure that transitions between modalities are seamless, purposeful, and pedagogically justified rather than merely technological.
- *Emphasize coherence and integration:* principles focus on maintaining social and temporal continuity across learning experiences (e.g., online collaborative tasks that feed into in-person group discussions and vice versa).
- *Embed flexibility and accessibility:* principles promote adaptable learning pathways, accessible resources, and inclusive participation opportunities (e.g., asynchronous catch-up options, multimodal materials).
- *Promote active, learner-centred engagement across modes:* principles highlight strategies for fostering agency and engagement regardless of learning mode (e.g., encourage learner autonomy in digital tasks while scaffolding collaboration in physical settings).
- *Leverage technology to extend pedagogy:* tool and technology use is guided by pedagogical intent; tools are selected and designed to enhance interaction, reflection, or personalization, not merely to digitize existing practices.
- *Integrate feedback and data loops across modalities:* design principles include mechanisms for gathering and using learning analytics from both online and face-to-face settings to inform ongoing redesign.

1.4.3. Principles for blended course and blended programme design

The EMBED's preliminaries emphasise intentional integration, pedagogical alignment, and organisation embedding of blended practices. Table 1 presents a comprehensive overview of the 10 design principles based on the evidence from the systematic review, linking each principle to the unique characteristics of BLEs (see Section 2) and illustrating how they can be operationalized at both course and programme levels.

The rationale behind this structure is twofold. First, blended learning environments possess unique features, such as the orchestration of multiple modalities, coherence across learning experiences, flexibility, and the integration of technology and data, that require intentional design. Mapping these characteristics to design principles ensures that pedagogical intent is maintained across both online and face-to-face components. Second, while all principles are applicable at both course and programme levels, their implementation differs in focus and

granularity. At the course level, principles guide the design of specific learning activities and scaffolds, among others. At the programme level, they support for example consistent use of technology, and cross-module alignment. By linking BLE characteristics to actionable principles at both levels, the table provides educators and programme designers with a practical tool to translate the theoretical foundations into educational practice. This approach ensures that blended practices are not merely a combination of modalities, but a thoughtfully orchestrated educational experience.

Table 1*Design principles and level-specific applications*

Design principle	Blended learning environment characteristic	Course-level application	Programme-level application
1. Embed active learning	Active, learner-centred engagement across modes; Orchestration of modalities and spaces	Design participatory sequences combining online and face-to-face tasks; align reflection, discussion, and problem-solving activities	Ensure programme-wide coherence of active learning approaches across modules; sequence progressive skill-building experiences
2. Integrate assessment & feedback	Integrate feedback and data loops across modalities; Coherence and integration	Embed formative and summative assessments aligned with activities; provide timely, personalized feedback; use analytics to guide learning	Coordinate assessment strategy across courses; monitor progression using learning analytics; align standards, rubrics, and feedback timing
3. Scaffold learning	Active, learner-centred engagement; Coherence and integration; Orchestration of modalities	Stage learning pathways; provide structured pre-class, in-class, and post-class support; adapt complexity gradually	Ensure cross-course scaffolding of skills and knowledge; plan year-on-year progression pathways and shared preparatory resources
4. Foster learner autonomy	Flexibility and accessibility; Active, learner-centred engagement	Offer self-paced learning options, choices in tasks and modalities; embed reflection and goal-setting	Provide flexible programme pathways, electives, and organisational support to develop self-regulation and adaptive learning skills
5. Support collaborative & social learning	Coherence and integration; Active, learner-centred engagement	Integrate peer collaboration, group projects, peer review; design synchronous and asynchronous interaction	Establish programme-level collaborative projects, learning communities, and cross-module peer engagement initiatives
6. Ensure constructive & curriculum alignment	Orchestration of modalities and spaces; Coherence and integration	Align objectives, activities, and assessments within a course; make connections between online and face-to-face explicit	Map outcomes, activities, and assessments across the programme; ensure continuity, progression, and coherent student experience
7. Apply inclusive & motivational design	Flexibility and accessibility	Use Universal Design for Learning principles; provide multiple engagement pathways, culturally responsive tasks, and motivational strategies	Set inclusive programme standards; monitor workload, accessibility, and engagement equity across courses
8. Embed real-world relevance	Active, learner-centred engagement; Orchestration of modalities and spaces	Design authentic, workplace-relevant tasks and projects; integrate simulations and problem-based learning	Coordinate partnerships and interdisciplinary challenges; sequence tasks to progressively build professional and academic competences
9. Integrate technology as a pedagogical enabler	Leverage technology to extend pedagogy; Integrate feedback and data loops	Select tools to enhance learning, reflection, and feedback; use simulations, analytics, and adaptive platforms	Develop a consistent technology ecosystem across courses; enable analytics-informed decisions, scalability, and cross-course coherence
10. Use frameworks and iterative design approaches	Integrate feedback and data loops; Coherence and integration	Apply frameworks (ADDIE, SAM, BOPPPS) and iterative design cycles to refine course design	Establish programme-level design processes; coordinate iterative improvements, stakeholder feedback, and cross-course alignment

1.4.4. Data-driven and smart learning environments as blended ecosystems

Two critical types of learning environments in this continuum - data-driven learning environments (DDLEs) and smart learning environments (SLEs) - extend the foundational stages of blended practice. SLEs are considered a higher-maturity stage, combining data-driven principles with autonomous, context-aware adaptations.

1. DDLEs are educational settings where learning design, teaching strategies, and student support are continuously informed and optimized through systematic collection and analysis of data derived from learner interactions, behaviours, and performance. Core features include learning analytics to monitor performance and engagement, personalized feedback, and adaptive pathways, with interventions guided by empirical evidence. While DDLEs leverage evidence to improve instructional decisions, they are typically reactive: adaptations occur based on analysed data rather than autonomously. As Ifenthaler and Yau (2020) note, DDLEs are characterized by environments in which “learning decisions and interventions are guided by systematic analysis of learning data” (p. 2).
2. In line with García-Tudela and colleagues’ foundational work (2021), a SLE is an educational setting that integrates advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence and learning analytics, to create adaptive, personalized, and context-aware learning experiences. Key features include real-time integration of multiple data sources, proactive and autonomous adaptation to learner needs, support for both students and educators in decision-making, and incorporation of predictive analytics, automated scaffolding, and real-time feedback. From a maturity perspective, SLEs represent a more advanced stage, where the system not only analyses data but autonomously adjusts and enhances the learning experience (García-Tudela et al., 2021).

Table 2
Differences between a data-driven and smart learning environment

Feature	Data-driven learning environment (DDLE)	Smart learning environment (SLE)
Goal	Evidence-based teaching and personalized support	Fully adaptive, seamless, learner-centered experience
Data use	Primarily for monitoring and informing decisions	Real-time, adaptive, predictive, and context-aware
Adaptivity	Usually requires human interpretation	Autonomous or semi-autonomous adaptation
Technology	Learning analytics tools	AI, IoT, sensors, real-time dashboards, learning analytics

2. About maturity and change

2.1. Continuous Quality Improvement in the blended higher education ecosystem

Blended higher education increasingly requires a dual focus that links course-level quality with broader institutional maturity, recognising that effective quality assurance (QA) must account for the multidimensional, digital technology-driven nature of teaching and learning. Rather than treating a set of isolated courses, research argues for a systemic, ecosystem perspective in which pedagogical, technological, human, and organizational layers interact to shape learner experiences and institutional capacity. Continuous quality improvement (CQI) depends on connecting top-down innovation policies with bottom-up digital transformation, ensuring that strategic frameworks enable local experimentation while grassroots practices inform institutional decision-making. Within this ecosystem, coherent course and programme design, robust and interoperable technological infrastructures, sustained investment in faculty and student capacity building, and aligned strategies and policies are all essential for developing a sustainable quality culture. Because each layer influences the others, QA must operate as a dynamic feedback system that uses standards, analytics, and context-sensitive evaluation to drive ongoing improvement across both micro and macro levels of blended higher education.

2.2. A matter of (managing) educational change

2.2.1. Progress from ad hoc to sustainable

The development of blended education within higher education institutions can be understood as a process of managing complex educational change. This transformation involves a gradual shift in design culture, decision-making, and adaptability: moving from fragmented, individual initiatives toward systemic, data-informed, and context-aware educational ecosystems. The evolution across the four maturity stages - ad hoc, intentional, diagnostic, and sustainable - reflects how organisations increasingly integrate pedagogical, technological, and organisational intelligence into their educational practice.

At the heart of this process lie three interconnected dimensions of change: design and development thinking, use of data and evidence, and adaptivity and context-awareness. Each dimension reveals a distinct developmental logic that describes how blended practices mature through intentionality, systematicity, and adaptivity.

Table 3*From ad hoc to sustainable educational ecosystems*

Dimension	Ad hoc → Intentional	Intentional → Diagnostic	Diagnostic → Sustainable
Thinking and decision making about design and development	From ad hoc decisions to purposeful design of blended approaches.	From intentionality to systematic, evidence-informed design based on shared principles.	From systematic to adaptive and autonomous design based on real-time feedback and research.
Using data and integrating evidence in practices	Anecdotal reflection.	Structured collection and analysis of feedback data.	Continuous analytics and predictive data use guiding design and decision-making.
Including adaptivity and context-awareness	Limited flexibility, fixed pacing.	Context-sensitive design accounting for learner diversity.	Context-aware systems and organisational adaptivity creating personalized and inclusive ecosystems.

Thinking and decision making about blended design and development progresses from ad hoc and fragmented course-level initiatives toward coherent, adaptive systems of design. At the ad hoc stage, blended teaching often emerges informally, driven by individual educators experimenting with online tools or formats. As organisations transition to the intentional stage, design efforts become intentional: educators plan proportions and sequences of online and face-to-face activities in alignment with pedagogical goals. Moving toward the diagnostic stage, design practices are systematised and guided by shared organisational principles, evidence, and feedback mechanisms. Finally, at the sustainable stage, design becomes adaptive and autonomous - supported by real-time analytics, artificial intelligence, and research-informed design frameworks that continuously adjust to learners' evolving needs.

The use of data and evidence follows a similar trajectory. Early-stage blended initiatives rely largely on anecdotal reflection and informal feedback from learners and staff. As maturity develops, organisations introduce structured data collection, e.g. course evaluations, learning analytics, and usage statistics, to inform iterative improvements. In the diagnostic stage, these processes become embedded in organisational routines, enabling systematic monitoring of learning outcomes and teaching effectiveness. Ultimately, in sustainable environments, data are not only collected and analyzed but used predictively and adaptively. Continuous analytics inform real-time decision-making, guiding both educators and learners toward more effective T&L pathways and strategies.

The third maturity dimension, *adaptivity and context-awareness*, captures how responsiveness to learner diversity and contextual variation becomes increasingly sophisticated. In the ad hoc stage, flexibility is minimal and pacing is largely fixed. As blended teaching becomes more deliberate, educators start to design for diverse needs and contexts, offering differentiated pathways and pacing options. At the diagnostic stage, data are used to tailor experiences to individual or group profiles, supporting inclusiveness and personalization. In sustainable environments, adaptivity extends beyond the classroom: systems and organisations themselves become context-aware. They autonomously adjust

learning environments, resources, and support services based on real-time data, creating genuinely personalized and inclusive learning ecosystems.

Together, these dimensions highlight that maturity in blended education is not merely about increased technology use or process efficiency - it is fundamentally about managing educational change. It requires cultivating a culture of design thinking, evidence-informed decision-making, and systemic adaptivity that transforms not only T&L practices but also the organisational capacity to sustain innovation. The movement from ad hoc to sustainable blended education thus represents a developmental journey from reactivity to intentionality, from intentionality to systematization, and ultimately from systematization to intelligent adaptivity - a shift from managing change to enabling continuous transformation.

2.2.2. Innovations and educational change

In higher education (HE), it is crucial to distinguish between *invention*, the discovery and development of new technological products or processes, and *innovation*, the adoption and utilization of such inventions (Weiss & Birnbaum, 1989). More broadly, innovation can be understood as “a new way of doing things” (Zolla, 1999). The design and development of intelligent technologies are guided both by the intrinsic logic of the technology and the needs of its users. While radical transformations are possible, continuity typically predominates over abrupt disruption (Punie, 2000).

The introduction of digital technologies in HE constitutes a cyclical process of change (Fisser, 2001). Every educational change, whether incremental or systemic, demands adaptation among people, technologies, structures, and tasks. The greater the number of interdependent changes, the higher the risk, highlighting the importance of anticipating the magnitude of change. O’Hara et al. (1999) identified three levels of change:

1. First-order change: modifies tasks only (e.g., automating previously manual work).
2. Second-order change: alters interactions between people, tasks, and technology, affecting procedures and roles.
3. Third-order change: transforms all organizational components - technology, tasks, people, and structure - potentially reshaping power relations and organisational functioning.

Change generates uncertainty, resistance, and adaptation, often manifesting as concern, confusion, or even despair. The magnitude and scope of change influence the intensity of these responses, with *driver technologies* - those requiring comprehensive organizational, procedural, and strategic transformation - posing greater challenges than *enabler technologies*, which involve comparatively limited risk (Kabat, 1994). Educators, for example, must comprehend the technology conceptually and apply it pedagogically, adjusting *what and how* they teach (Cheung, 1999).

Table 4
Effective management of educational change

Level of change	Actor	Key challenges	Concerted actions
First-order	IT teams, instructional designers	Usability, lack of training	Provide user-friendly design templates, onboarding, and helpdesk support
Second-order	Department chairs, teaching & learning centres	Role confusion, workflow disruption	Facilitate communities of practice; co-design procedures
Third-order	Senior leadership, governing boards	Cultural resistance, misaligned incentives	Align policies and rewards; foster participatory dialogue

Effective management of educational change requires coordinated action across all levels to overcoming resistance and fostering adoption. IT teams and instructional designers address task-level challenges, department chairs and teaching centers handle process-level adaptations, and senior leadership ensures systemic alignment and cultural support.

2.3. Strategies for change in higher education

Successful organizational change within complex institutions such as universities requires a systemic, well-sequenced approach that recognizes the importance of each phase in the change process. Fullan (1991) proposed a three-phase integration model for higher education. Each stage requires specific actors to address challenges with concerted actions. Real-world examples demonstrate that staged support, digital strategies and the onset of a toolkit enhances the likelihood of successful organisational adoption. In the UK, for example, different HEIs have employed resources from a digital transformation toolkit (Jisc, 2023; Newman et al., 2025). As outlined by Elton (1999), institutional transformation unfolds in three interrelated stages: *unfreezing*, *changing*, and *refreezing*. For example, when a university aims to implement a new digital learning platform, leaders might plan a phased rollout aligned with this framework to ensure that change occurs in manageable, sustainable segments.

1. *Preparing the ground for change (Unfreezing)*: This phase focuses on creating readiness for transformation by reducing resistance, destabilizing existing routines, and communicating a clear vision. Leadership aligns policies, secures funding, and signals strategic priorities, while HR and mentors foster reflective spaces, peer networks, and cultural openness. Awareness campaigns, success stories, and stakeholder engagement generate institutional momentum for change.
2. *Implementing and embedding innovation (Changing)*: In this phase, universities actively experiment, build capacity, and engage stakeholders. Top-down facilitation and bottom-up initiatives combine through pilot projects, workshops, and feedback loops. Incentives, recognition, and CPD support voluntary participation, while transparent leadership balances guidance, education, and motivation to overcome resistance and gradually scale effective practices.

3. *Institutionalizing sustainable practice (Refreezing)*: The final phase consolidates new practices into routines and structures to ensure sustainability. Policies, workload models, QA systems, and governance embed blended or digital teaching into institutional processes. Continuous technical and pedagogical support, alongside reliable and interoperable technologies, reinforces adoption, while strategic review and resource planning maintain long-term transformation.

Based on Elton (1999), Fullan (1991) and Newman et al. (2025) Table 5 was established. It integrates three complementary frameworks for digital transformation in higher education, mapping the three phases of change to actors, challenges, and concrete actions. It highlights which stakeholders are involved at each stage, from senior leadership and change agents to faculty, QA units, and IT services, while identifying common barriers such as resistance, skill gaps, and technological bottlenecks. The table also consolidates practical interventions, including communication strategies, pilot projects, professional development, digital culture building, policy embedding, and continuous evaluation, providing a comprehensive roadmap for planning and sustaining institutional change.

Table 5

Digital transformation in higher education: actors, challenges and actions

Phase	Core actions	Key Actors	Challenges	HE Examples
Unfreezing (Mobilization)	Build urgency, reduce resistance; decision-making to adopt digital innovation	Senior staff, university leaders, change agents	Low awareness, fear of disruption, resistance to change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Articulate a clear digital vision linked to institutional mission ▪ Communicate benefits using case studies and toolkit resources ▪ Pilot small-scale projects to demonstrate quick wins and strategic alignment ▪ Embed digital strategy in policies and funding frameworks
Changing (Initial Use)	Implement innovation, train, incentivize, co-design courses, apply learning analytics	Faculty, instructional designers, department chairs, support teams, HR services, mentors	Skill gaps, resistance, uneven adoption, fear of failure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provide CPD/training and mentoring using toolkit templates and maturity models ▪ Build peer networks and reflective spaces for collaborative learning ▪ Co-design courses and apply learning analytics to improve teaching ▪ Emphasize digital culture development and stakeholder engagement to overcome resistance

Table 5 - Continued

Phase	Core actions	Key Actors	Challenges	HE Examples
Refreezing (Institutionalisation)	Institutionalize and sustain innovation; embed into routines, policies, and structures; ensure technological reliability	QA units, governance bodies, IT services, vendors, CPD offices	Fatigue, uneven adoption, technological bottlenecks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrate blended T&L into policy, workload models, and evaluation systems ▪ Ensure system interoperability and stable performance ▪ Use toolkit-supported maturity model for continuous review, assessment, and professional development ▪ Promote a culture of CQI and wider adoption through ongoing engagement and feedback loops

Likewise, Ping Lim et al. (2019) underscore that sustained digital change requires a holistic approach: leadership must visibly endorse the vision, support staff through targeted professional development, and embed practices within institutional policies and quality systems. Figure 3 encapsulates a multi-dimensional model that illustrates how various strategic components come together to support blended initiatives at the organisation level. Addressing these seven key strategic dimensions systematically can enhance the likelihood of sustained practices in HEIs. This coordinated effort helps to overcome resistance, maintain momentum, and scale up BL practices effectively.

Figure 1
Strategic planning of HEIs for blended learning (Ping Lim et al., 2019)

2.4. Personal innovation-decision process and continuous professional development

An organization must reach a critical mass where sufficient individuals adopt the innovation for it to become self-sustaining. Early adopters (“pioneers” or “self-starters”) often drive initial uptake, while more cautious faculty require targeted support and incentives (Hagner, 2000). Cheung (1999) refined Rogers’ (1995) Innovation-Decision Process model for educational contexts. This outlines the stages individuals undergo when adopting an innovation: knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation, and confirmation. Cheung subdivided the implementation phase into experiment, adjustment, mastery, and personalization (Figure 2). This nuanced understanding highlights that adoption is neither linear nor uniform and emphasizes the importance of contextualized, educator-centered support. Technological innovations possess characteristics that influence adoption speed: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability (Rogers, 1995; Beyers, 2002).

Figure 2
Implementation phases (Cheung, 1999)

This model provides a detailed framework that highlights the various stages and phases educators go through when adopting an innovation, specifically the four phases within the implementation stage: experiment, adjustment, mastery, and personalization. By understanding these phases and their associated phenomena and coping strategies, trainers can tailor in-service programs to better support educators at each stage.

Specifically, the model suggests that continuous professional development (CPD) tailored to each phase improve adoption outcomes. A training program should further align with principles such as educator ownership and contextual relevance. They should be evidence-informed and phase-sensitive, namely:

1. Experiment: build confidence, encourage trial-and-error.
2. Adjustment: address contextual barriers, provide guidance, encourage reflection.
3. Mastery: consolidate skills, promote best practices.
4. Personalization: support individual adaptation and innovation.

Incorporating opportunities for educators to share ongoing experiences is crucial, as it helps educators understand their own development and reduces uncertainties related to change.

3. EMBED+: Structure and logic of the model's dimensions and maturity levels

3.1. Advancing maturity: changes

The EMBED+ framework intends to offer a comprehensive approach to understanding and developing blended approaches in higher education. Drawing on the systematic review of studies and use case assessment, refinements aim to increase the EMBED+'s practical and strategic relevance. The framework now explicitly incorporates organisational support and infrastructure, with procurement practices and digital resources that facilitate the adoption and scaling of blended T&L across all levels. A fourth dimension, focusing on digital sovereignty and sustainable digital learning ecosystems, acknowledges organisations that retain control over learning platforms, data storage, and applications, promoting autonomy, ethical technology use, and long-term stability.

In a latter stage, the EMBED+ project partners will further differentiate its deliverables by stakeholder perspective, recognizing that educators, instructional designers, programme teams, and institutional leaders require distinct levels of detail and framing to operationalize maturity effectively. Grounding the framework in real-life examples further strengthens its applicability, illustrating how each maturity stage manifests at the course, programme, and organizational levels.

3.2. Advancing maturity: key dimensions

EMBED+ conceptualizes BLEs along a maturity continuum with four progressive stages: *Ad hoc, Intentional, Diagnostic, and Sustainable*. This continuum reflects the evolving complexity: each maturity stage builds on the previous one, moving from individualized, fragmented efforts toward coordinated, evidence-informed, and strategically embedded blended practices.

Maturity progression is captured through three key features (with a guiding question between brackets):

Design and development thinking (What works?)

Examines how blended courses and programmes are conceived and designed, and how organisational operations, policies, and regulations are developed to enable effective and sustainable blended practices.

Use of data and evidence (What works and how can it be improved?)

Focuses on what outcomes (e.g., efficiency, effectiveness, satisfaction) are systematically collected, how these data are analysed and applied to inform iterative improvement, and how insights from both practice and research are used to drive meaningful change.

Adaptivity and context-awareness (What works in a given context, and how can it be improved?)

Adaptivity and context-awareness assess how effectively blended environments respond to the needs of learners, educators, and institutions, ensuring flexible, personalized, and inclusive learning experiences.

Each maturity level captures a distinct stage of development. The Ad hoc stage marks the starting point, characterized by fragmented activities, limited coordination across courses, programmes, and organizational structures, minimal data collection, and reliance on individual initiative rather than coordinated strategy. The Intentional stage introduces purposeful planning and structured design. At this level, courses and programmes incorporate blended elements intentionally, and institutions begin to support blended education through strategic priorities and policy references. Data collection and the use of evidence emerge, though practices are often inconsistent or localized. The Sustainable stage represents a systematic and structured approach to blended T&L. Organizational principles guide course and programme design, outcomes data are regularly collected, analysed, and applied to inform continuous improvement, and learning analytics and dashboards support evidence-informed decision-making. Finally, the Sustainable stage embodies the highest level of maturity, in which design, data, and research evidence are fully integrated. Blended practices are embedded in everyday academic operations, professional development, and governance, with adaptivity, inclusiveness, personalization, and sustainability prioritized across courses, programmes, and institutional policies, fostering a culture of continuous improvement.

3.3. Advancing maturity: multilevel perspective

EMBED+ underscores that maturity is inherently multi-layered. Courses serve as the core unit of development, programmes ensure coherence across multiple courses, and organizations provide the structures, policies, and resources necessary to sustain and scale improvement.

EMBED+ evaluates maturity across three actor levels: course, programme, and organization. At the course level, the framework focuses on the design of individual learning experiences, pedagogical activities, assessment, and student engagement. The programme level ensures coherence across courses, supports curricular progression, and aligns learning outcomes with broader educational objectives. At the organizational level, maturity encompasses institutional policies, governance structures, digital infrastructure, and professional development initiatives that sustain and scale T&L. By considering these three levels, EMBED+ provides a multilevel perspective that enables institutions to understand

progression from basic to advanced implementation, align strategic priorities, identify gaps, and establish a shared understanding of blended practices' maturity.

Below is a short-version, general maturity matrix, based on the assumptions about maturity. It is presented so that scholars, instructional designers, programme directors, and institutional leaders can quickly assess maturity, identify next steps, and compare levels across actors. Each cell includes a description, 2-3 practical indicators, aligned with the 4 maturity levels and three actor levels (course, programme, organisation).

Table 8

Enactment of blended maturity at the course, programme and organisation level

Maturity Level	Course level	Programme level	Organisation level
1. Ad hoc	<p>Blended elements are unplanned and inconsistent. Activities depend on individual educator preference. Tool and media use is minimal or optional.</p> <p>Indicators: No articulated blended design; no data use; inconsistent student experience.</p>	<p>No coordination across courses. Programmes lack a shared vision or expectations for blended T&L.</p> <p>Indicators: Large variation between courses; no progression model; no shared workload or modality planning.</p>	<p>No organisational strategy or support. Digital tools exist but are fragmented and unsupported.</p> <p>Indicators: No policies; no staff training; infrastructure varies by faculty or unit.</p>
2. Intentional	<p>Blended design is deliberate and aligned with learning outcomes. Technology is used purposefully.</p> <p>Indicators: Clearly structured online & face-to-face activities; some evaluation or reflection; educators experiment with new methods.</p>	<p>Programme-level alignment emerges. Shared expectations for blended T&L; curriculum pathways begin to integrate modalities.</p> <p>Indicators: Programme agreements on contact hours, modality balance, and assessment; periodic review meetings.</p>	<p>Blended T&L is recognized in strategy. Organisational policies and PD opportunities support emerging blended practices.</p> <p>Indicators: Basic guidelines; workshops; LMS and core tools centrally supported.</p>
3. Diagnostic	<p>Course design is continuously improved using data. Learning analytics, feedback, and student performance inform redesign.</p> <p>Indicators: Analytics dashboards used; assessment redesigned based on evidence; accessibility issues monitored.</p>	<p>Programmes use aggregated data to enhance coherence and progression. Decisions are evidence-informed.</p> <p>Indicators: Data on progression and dropout used; systematic curriculum review; shared monitoring of students' learning experience.</p>	<p>Organisation-wide governance and quality systems support blended T&L. Infrastructure is stable and centrally coordinated.</p> <p>Indicators: Dashboards at course/programme/organisation level; formal governance; recurring PD; QA processes include blended T&L criteria.</p>
4. Sustainable	<p>Courses are adaptive, inclusive, and personalized. Digital tools support real-time feedback and differentiated pathways.</p> <p>Indicators: Course-level dashboards; course adaptivity; AI-supported feedback; UDL principles embedded.</p>	<p>Programmes function as coherent, data-rich ecosystems. Continuous improvement cycles integrate research, analytics, and stakeholder input.</p> <p>Indicators: Programme-level dashboards with learning analytics; cross-course adaptivity; long-term evaluation loops.</p>	<p>Blended approaches are fully embedded in organisational culture, governance, and infrastructure. Digital sovereignty and sustainable ecosystems are established.</p> <p>Indicators: Organisation controls or strategically governs platforms; long-term investment plans; embedded continuous PD (CPD); strategic innovation cycles.</p>

3.4. Advancing blended courses, programmes and organisations

3.4.1. Dimensions and indicators at course level

At the course level, where the core teaching and learning processes are designed, enacted, and continuously improved, the EMBED+Matrix captures how blended courses mature across key dimensions. It includes the following 7 dimensions across 4 maturity levels:

1. **Proportioning and sequencing of online and face-to-face learning activities:** the organisation of online and face-to-face components in a blended course to create a learning pathway with transitions and alignment to learning outcomes.
2. **Selection of tools and media:** the choice of digital and analogue instruments, applications or platforms used to perform learning tasks (e.g., discussion forums, polling apps, lab equipment, simulation software) and formats or channels through which learning content is delivered or represented (e.g., video, audio, text, interactive simulations, slide decks).
3. **Course flexibility:** the incorporation of adaptable pace, modality, activity options, or resources within the blended course.
4. **Course interaction:** the setup and facilitation of learner–learner, learner–educator, learner–content, and learner–IS interactions across online and face-to-face settings.
5. **Course learner guidance:** structured guidance that build students’ (self-regulated) learning skills, helping them plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning across online and face-to-face modalities.
6. **Course load:** the estimation, coordination, and monitoring of study load across online and face-to-face activities within the course.
7. **Inclusiveness:** the tailoring the learning experience to the diverse needs and backgrounds of all students, including accessibility, sense of belonging, cultural responsiveness, equitable learning pathways.

3.4.2. Maturity matrix at course level

Table 9

Summary of blended maturity at the course level, with examples

Course dimension	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
1. Course design: Proportioning and sequencing of online and face-to-face activities	<p>Activities added independently; connections to learning outcomes or assessments are accidental.</p> <p><i>Example: Two courses teach the same skill with different tools and grading methods, no explicit transition.</i></p>	<p>Activities deliberately follow a coherent learning logic aligned to learning outcomes. Transitions between modalities are explained but not always reinforced.</p> <p><i>Example: Pre-class video supports in-class application; assessment relates to both</i></p>	<p>Activities refined based on engagement, performance, and progression; problematic sequences are corrected.</p> <p><i>Example: Workshop is rescheduled after many students fail preparatory quizzes.</i></p>	<p>Online and face-to-face components form a seamless, adaptive pathway fully aligned with learning outcomes and assessments.</p> <p><i>Example: Pre-class modules branch automatically based on prior quiz results; in-class activities adapt to progress.</i></p>
2. Course design: Selection of tools and media	<p>Tools chosen for convenience; inconsistent use across course; limited accessibility.</p> <p><i>Example: PDFs and uncaptioned lecture recordings are uploaded</i></p>	<p>Tools support pedagogy, feedback, and collaboration; basic accessibility provided.</p> <p><i>Example: Captions added; discussion board introduced for peer interaction</i></p>	<p>Tools refined or replaced based on engagement, completion, and student feedback.</p> <p><i>Example: Long lecture video replaced by multiple short videos after low watch-time.</i></p>	<p>Integrated tool ecosystem allows multiple formats aligned with learning outcomes; supports personalised and inclusive engagement.</p> <p><i>Example: Students choose text, video, simulation, or worked examples for the same content.</i></p>
3. Course flexibility	<p>Single mandatory pathway; no accommodation for different learner needs.</p> <p><i>Example: Attendance strictly synchronous; no alternatives.</i></p>	<p>Limited options in pacing, modality, or activity type for common constraints.</p> <p><i>Example: Recorded sessions provided for commuters.</i></p>	<p>Flexibility expanded based on participation and performance; targeted support offered.</p> <p><i>Example: Asynchronous alternative added when live session missed by many.</i></p>	<p>Personalised pathways adapt dynamically to learner performance, preferences, and context.</p> <p><i>Example: Students select project-based or practice-based routes aligned to outcomes.</i></p>
4. Course interaction	<p>Interaction incidental; students left to engage independently.</p> <p><i>Example: Discussion forum exists but remains unused.</i></p>	<p>Structured interaction with prompts, roles, and periodic facilitation.</p> <p><i>Example: Weekly discussion questions with instructor synthesis.</i></p>	<p>Interaction redesigned based on engagement and peer review; groupings or tasks adjusted.</p> <p><i>Example: Peer review added after shallow forum participation detected.</i></p>	<p>Rich, inclusive collaboration ecosystem; groups and interactions adapt to learner strengths, participation, and equity.</p> <p><i>Example: Groups formed to balance skills; roles rotated; silent participants supported.</i></p>

Table 9 – continued

Course dimension	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
5. Course learner guidance	Minimal or inconsistent guidance; learners expected to manage independently. <i>Example: Grades returned with no explanatory feedback.</i>	Shared guidance provided via checklists, exemplars, and weekly planning support. <i>Example: Weekly planner and sample assignment shared.</i>	Targeted support provided based on engagement, performance, or early warning signs. <i>Example: Students missing tasks receive personalised nudges.</i>	Fully integrated support system fostering self-regulated learning; personalised, culturally responsive, and inclusive. <i>Example: Learners receive AI-driven recommendations for reflection, remedial practice, or advanced tasks.</i>
6. Course load	Workload uneven, clustered, and uncoordinated; assessment peaks common. <i>Example: Readings, quiz, and project due in same week.</i>	Workload estimated and planned; minor adjustments to reduce peaks. <i>Example: Reading load reduced after student complaints.</i>	Workload adjusted based on observed engagement, time-on-task, or completion rates. <i>Example: Quiz deadline moved after analytics reveal high workload week.</i>	Workload balanced and sequenced to support progressive learning; pacing options personalised. <i>Example: Students choose between standard and extended weekly pace to match progress.</i>
7. Inclusiveness	Course assumes a single learner type; accessibility and diversity largely ignore <i>Example: High-bandwidth video required with no alternatives.</i>	Basic accessibility and diverse representation implemented. <i>Example: Captions provided; examples reflect multiple perspectives.</i>	Materials and activities revised when inequities are detected; multiple formats provided. <i>Example: Simplified texts offered after identifying reading challenges among some students.</i>	UDL principles and culturally sustaining pedagogy embedded; multiple personalised pathways and contextually relevant content available. <i>Example: Students select case studies aligned to cultural or professional context; adaptive materials delivered based on prior performance.</i>

Note. Maturity levels progress is based on: (1) thinking and decision making about design and development; (2) use of data and evidence; (3) adaptivity or context-awareness.

Table 10

Enactment of blended maturity at the course level, per maturity feature

Course dimension	Maturity features	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
1. Proportioning and sequencing of online and face-to-face activities	Design and development (alignment, transitions, scaffolding)	Activities are added without a clear design rationale or alignment with learning goals. Online and face-to-face components function largely independently. Transitions are unclear or implicit; students must infer how activities relate across modalities.	Activities are deliberately designed using literature, models, or design principles (e.g. flipped classroom with pre-class videos followed by in-class application tasks). Learning goals guide activity selection. Transitions are explained and partially guided, though not consistently.	Sequence and structure are refined using learning analytics and feedback (e.g. identifying drop-off points or concept bottlenecks). Transitions are clearly explained and supported where students struggle or disengage.	A coherent, flexible learning pathway is continuously improved using a design framework and ongoing data. Learning goals, activities, and assessments are fully aligned. Transitions are seamless, adaptive, and personalised, with scaffolding gradually faded as students gain independence.
	Data and evidence (learning flow, coherence)	No monitoring of learning flow or coherence; decisions based on anecdotal evidence.	Descriptive analytics and professional judgement used (e.g. completion rates, attendance, basic LMS usage, learner surveys).	Learning analytics identify problematic sequencing (e.g. skipped activities, low engagement, problematic transitions).	Continuous multi-source refinement using longitudinal and predictive analytics (performance, engagement, formative data, sentiment).
	Adaptivity and context-awareness (sequencing, personalisation)	Fixed sequencing regardless of learner needs.	Basic pacing guidance and optional activities provided.	Sequence adjusts based on performance or needs.	Multiple learning pathways automatically surfaced.
2. Selection of tools and media	Design and development (technology enhances pedagogy)	Tools chosen for convenience; technology used mainly for content storage.	Tools chosen strategically to support pedagogy, collaboration, feedback, and assessment.	Tools periodically replaced or upgraded based on usage analytics.	Evidence-based tool ecosystem aligned with learning outcomes, design principles, and future workplace demands.
	Data and evidence (impact measurement)	No data collected.	Usability surveys and student preference feedback considered.	Data-informed optimisation (video drop-off, quiz attempts, interaction heat maps, cognitive load indicators).	Long-term learning impact analytics used in research-informed tool decisions.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness (accessibility, UDL)	Accessibility ignored.	Basic accessibility (captions, alternative formats).	Format switching based on evidence (e.g. shorter videos where long ones are abandoned).	Multiple equivalent modality options (video, audio, text, simulation); students choose format.
3. Course flexibility	Design and development (choice, autonomy)	Single mandatory learning pathway.	Limited choice (recordings, flexible deadlines, hybrid sessions).	Flexibility expanded based on dropout data or student requests.	Personalised adaptive pathways based on performance, interests, language, or background.
	Data and evidence	None.	Attendance and basic LMS usage metrics.	Decisions informed by completion rates, late submissions, and workload analytics.	Predictive analytics automatically offer pacing and pathway recommendations.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Reactive adjustments only after failure.	Anticipation of typical constraints (working students, commuters).	Custom supports (catch-up weeks, alternative assessments during peak load).	Multiple equivalent pathways (e.g. project, simulation, quiz track).

Table 10 – continued

Course dimension	Maturity features	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
4. Course interaction	Design and development (collaborative, social learning)	Interaction incidental; participation is hoped for rather than designed.	Structured interaction with prompts, roles, and feedback guidelines.	Interaction redesigned using participation and engagement analysis.	Rich interaction ecosystem: communities of inquiry, cross-group peer learning, collaborative creation workflows.
	Data and evidence	None tracked.	Counts of posts, replies, attendance.	Depth analytics (semantic analysis, network participation, peer-review quality).	Sentiment and equity analytics identify silent or marginalised learners.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	No facilitation.	Basic facilitation and summary posts.	Group composition or task structure adjusted when engagement drops.	Adaptive group formation (analytics-based) and inclusive interaction routines (e.g. rotating roles).
5. Course learner guidance	Design and development	Minimal guidance; requirements unclear.	Checklists, exemplars, and weekly planning guidance.	Targeted supports triggered by analytics.	Fully integrated SRL framework: students plan, monitor, evaluate, and adjust learning with systemic support.
	Data and evidence	None.	Basic tracking (submission timing, performance).	Early-alert dashboards and behavioural triggers.	Personal learning analytics dashboards for real-time goal tracking.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Same support for all learners.	Basic differentiation (FAQ, office hours).	Tailored supports for struggling versus advanced learners.	Culturally, linguistically, and needs-responsive individualised support.
6. Course load	Design and development	Overload and clustering common; no coordination.	Study load estimated and aligned to expected effort.	Dynamic adjustments based on time-on-task analytics.	Balanced study load verified longitudinally across cohorts.
	Data and evidence	None.	Workload surveys.	LMS completion, time-spent tracking, task audits.	Benchmarking load patterns across cohorts and programmes.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Rigid deadlines regardless of stress peaks.	Some deadline flexibility.	Course work redistributed based on weekly analytics.	Personalised pacing routes (standard vs extended).
7. Inclusiveness	Design and development	Course assumes a single “normative” learner; inclusion absent.	Basic accessibility features; some diverse examples included.	Course redesigned based on participation, access, and performance data.	UDL and culturally sustaining pedagogies fully embedded; diversity anticipated from the outset.
	Data and evidence	No equity or accessibility data.	Periodic feedback and usability checks.	Systematic tracking of participation gaps across groups and modalities.	Continuous equity monitoring with dashboards and documented decisions.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Accommodations only after complaints.	Minor proactive adjustments (language support, extended time).	Multiple equivalent formats and cognitively lighter pathways provided proactively.	Custom cultural and linguistic pathways; adaptive tools personalise difficulty, examples, and explanations.

3.4.3. Dimensions and indicators at programme level

A blended programme is a coherent set of courses in which the deliberate integration of blended T&L is implemented at programme level. This integration is supported and sustained by infrastructure, policy, professional development, and quality-assurance mechanisms. The main stakeholders of the programme level are educators, programme directors, students, quality officers, and sometimes also educational advisors, content developers, and higher management.

The EMBED+Matrix includes the following 5 dimensions across 4 maturity levels:

1. **Blended curriculum coherence and alignment:** the degree to which learning outcomes, teaching activities, assessment approaches, and online/face-to-face modalities are aligned across courses, ensuring learners experience a progressive, purposefully designed curriculum rather than isolated modules.
2. **Learning technologies and media:** how consistently the programme selects, integrates, and supports digital and non-digital tools, platforms, and media to enable learning activities and content delivery across courses.
3. **Programme flexibility:** the extent to which the programme accommodates different learner needs, profiles, and circumstances by providing options in pacing, modality, assessment formats, resource access, and learning pathways without compromising academic standards.
4. **Programme load:** how deliberately blended learning activities and assessments are proportioned and sequenced across courses and semesters to ensure a manageable student workload, avoid assessment clustering, and support sustained student progress in blended formats.
5. **Programme learner guidance:** how the programme supports students' learning processes by developing self-regulated learning skills, providing timely and meaningful feedback online/face-to-face modalities, and offering scaffolding (academic guidance, learning strategies, reflection) that evolves as learners progress.
6. **Programme capacity and sustainability:** the extent to which leadership, operations, and infrastructure systematically support, sustain, and align the human, technological, and organisational capacities required for quality blended T&L.

Below is a single comprehensive maturity matrix that consolidates all six blended-progress dimensions (Table 11). For each maturity indicator (design and development thinking and decision making; use of data and evidence; adaptivity and context-awareness), a concise description is provided. For every dimension, one or more illustrative examples is included to demonstrate maturity in practice.

3.4.4. Maturity matrix at programme level

Table 11

Summary of blended maturity at the programme level, with examples

Programme dimension	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
1. Blended curriculum coherence and alignment	<p>Courses are designed independently; alignment between learning outcomes, assessment, study load, and modalities occurs by coincidence. No monitoring of progression or coherence. Sequencing is fixed across semesters.</p> <p><i>Example: Two courses teach the same skill using different tools and assessment methods; assessment deadlines cluster unpredictably.</i></p>	<p>Programme is guided by a shared vision and basic design principles for alignment and modality use. Limited data (e.g. surveys) inform reflection. Basic sequencing rules are introduced.</p> <p><i>Example: Programme agrees that all modules use one rubric for collaborative projects and sets common assessment windows.</i></p>	<p>Systematic curriculum mapping (outcomes, assessments, scaffolding, modality plans) is conducted. Programme analytics inform alignment decisions and sequencing adjustments.</p> <p><i>Example: Progression and drop-out data reveal overload in one semester, leading to a revised assessment calendar.</i></p>	<p>Annual programme design cycle integrates cross-course projects, progression maps, and shared rubrics. Decisions are informed by longitudinal analytics and learning behaviour data. Multiple coherent pathways are supported.</p> <p><i>Example: Personalised programme routes and bachelor thesis projects are surfaced based on learner progress and preferences.</i></p>
2. Learning technologies and media	<p>Tool choice is driven by individual educator preference. No standards for accessibility or inclusiveness. No data on tool effectiveness. Students manage multiple platforms independently.</p> <p><i>Example: Five educators use five different submission tools; LMS navigation differs per course.</i></p>	<p>A minimum, centrally supported ecosystem is defined (e.g. LMS, video, peer-feedback tools). Occasional feedback highlights usability issues. Programme enforces basic tool consistency.</p> <p><i>Example: Programme shifts all assessment submissions into one LMS and provides a shared course template.</i></p>	<p>Tool selection is guided by programme-level principles and analytics (usage logs, helpdesk tickets, engagement). Tools support SRL, collaboration, and feedback.</p> <p><i>Example: Low forum engagement leads to replacement with a voice-note discussion tool across courses.</i></p>	<p>A strategically governed, interoperable ecosystem supports dashboards, personalised recommendations, and external stakeholder access. Predictive analytics inform tool choices.</p> <p><i>Example: Employer-validated e-portfolio follows students across the programme for competence development.</i></p>
3. Programme flexibility	<p>Flexibility occurs incidentally or through individual educator initiatives. Data is not gathered for improving flexibility. Adjustments are only made in exceptional cases.</p> <p><i>Example: All students follow the same programme without any choice for electives, pacing, or modality.</i></p>	<p>Some flexibility is purposefully embedded in the curriculum. Basic students' preferences are collected. Flexibility is mostly based on accessibility and inclusion concerns.</p> <p><i>Example: Programme offer electives based on interests of the students.</i></p>	<p>Flexibility model explicitly built into curriculum and SRL progression. Data (LMS, Attendance, Grades) provide supportive scaffolding and optional modules.</p> <p><i>Example: High fail rate early in year leads to new optional pre-semester SRL bootcamp.</i></p>	<p>Modular, stackable curriculum with micro-credentials, shared credits, and cross-institution mobility. Realtime analytics recommend personalised learning pathways, supportive scaffolding, and additional support.</p> <p><i>Example: Dashboard identifies mastery → student bypasses foundation module through challenge exam.</i></p>

Table 11 - Continued

Programme dimension	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
4. Programme load	<p>Study load is designed course-by-course with no coordination. No tracking of real workload or student time investment. Peak workloads remain hidden.</p> <p><i>Example: Four summative assignments are due in the same week across modules.</i></p>	<p>Programme plans indicative workload, modality distribution, and shared assessment calendars. Survey data occasionally informs adjustments.</p> <p><i>Example: Programme limits summative assessments to a maximum of two within a 14-day period.</i></p>	<p>Workload and sequencing are monitored using LMS activity, time-on-task, failed attempts, and dropout patterns. Adjustments are made semester-to-semester.</p> <p><i>Example: Workload data show Semester 1 overload, prompting staged submissions and redistributed deadlines.</i></p>	<p>Holistic progression of workload and complexity is mapped across the entire programme. Continuous improvement ensures equitable effort and authentic progression.</p> <p><i>Example: Balanced workload across a three-year curriculum aligned with industry-paced capstone projects.</i></p>
5. Programme learner guidance	<p>No shared expectations for feedback or scaffolding. Support varies widely; students navigate learning independently. No monitoring of feedback quality or workload.</p> <p><i>Example: Some courses provide only grades without comments.</i></p>	<p>Programme introduces shared feedback standards (timing, format, workload estimates). Surveys track satisfaction and support needs. Tutors respond to general trends.</p> <p><i>Example: Programme mandates mid-semester feedback in every module.</i></p>	<p>SRL pathway is explicitly mapped and progressively faded. LMS analytics monitor engagement, time-on-task, and workload spikes. Support is targeted by cohort or performance pattern.</p> <p><i>Example: Data show assessment overload → phased submissions with scaffolded instructions are introduced.</i></p>	<p>Full SRL curriculum is embedded, with adaptive, inclusive, and personalised support. Real-time alerts enable proactive intervention.</p> <p><i>Example: Automated alert signals missed checkpoints → tutor initiates personalised support session.</i></p>
6. Programme capacity and sustainability	<p>No programme-level guidance on blended models, tools, or pedagogy. Leadership involvement is minimal. No monitoring of blended practices; issues surface only through complaints. Contextual factors (access, skills, course type) are ignored.</p> <p><i>Example: Educators use different tools and blend models without rationale; no system tracks online participation.</i></p>	<p>Baseline expectations and basic policies for blended teaching are defined. Core tools and introductory PD are provided. Some metrics reviewed occasionally. Support is mostly reactive.</p> <p><i>Example: Shared LMS template is offered; PD workshops on flipped learning run at semester start.</i></p>	<p>Structured governance aligns course models, workload, technology, and support using systematic BTL data. Supports are adapted to course types and student groups.</p> <p><i>Example: Dashboards track participation and bottlenecks; PD is differentiated for flipped vs. hybrid courses.</i></p>	<p>Blended teaching is embedded in long-term programme strategy and culture. Integrated data streams drive continuous, anticipatory improvement. Enabling conditions evolve with pedagogy, technology, and learner diversity.</p> <p><i>Example: Governance group uses annual analytics, access audits, and workload data to redesign blend models; staff receive personalised PD pathways.</i></p>

Table 12*Enactment of blended maturity at the programme level, per maturity feature*

Programme dimension	Maturity feature	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
1. Blended curriculum coherence and alignment	Design and development	Courses are designed independently; connections between learning outcomes, assessment formats, study load, and/or learning modalities occur by coincidence.	Programme is based on a shared vision, a design methodology, and agreed-upon principles for alignment and modalities.	Systematic curriculum mapping is conducted across the programme.	Annual programme design cycle integrates cross-course projects, progression maps, and shared rubrics to ensure coherence and intentional sequencing.
	Data and evidence	No monitoring of progression, assessment clustering, or workload; decisions are based on anecdotal evidence.	Data are selectively gathered. Design choices rely mainly on professional judgement and experience, with limited or informal use of data.	Programme analytics and management data inform alignment decisions, including how online and face-to-face modes are distributed across courses.	Decisions are systematically informed by robust analytics, including longitudinal data on workload patterns, success rates, progression, and learning behaviours.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Fixed programme sequencing with no sensitivity to learner progression or coherence across semesters.	Basic sequencing adjustments are introduced (e.g. prerequisites, common assessment windows).	Programme sequencing and scaffolding are adjusted based on progression and drop-out data.	Multiple programme pathways and learning contents are dynamically surfaced based on learner data.
2. Learning technologies and media	Design and development	Tool choice is driven by individual educator preference; no shared standards for accessibility or inclusiveness.	A minimum, centrally supported ecosystem is defined (e.g. LMS, video tool, peer-feedback platform).	Tool selection is guided by programme-level principles and learning objectives.	Technology roadmap is aligned with learning outcomes, industry skills, institutional provisioning, and interoperability.
	Data and evidence	No data collected on engagement, usability, or workload related to tools.	Occasional student feedback highlights frustrations and tool overload.	Tool replacement decisions are driven by analytics (usage logs, helpdesk tickets, time-on-task).	Predictive analytics identify tools that enhance learning outcomes or self-regulated learning capacities.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Students manage multiple platforms independently.	Programme enforces tool consistency across modules.	Tools are selected to support SRL, access, collaboration, and feedback loops.	Integrated platforms support dashboards, personalised recommendations, and external stakeholder access.

Table 12 - continued

Programme dimension	Maturity feature	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
3. Programme flexibility	Design and development	Flexibility occurs incidentally or through individual educator initiatives, not as an intentional part of the programme design.	Programme flexibility is purposefully designed into some programme components, using literature, models, or shared design principles	Programme flexibility is intentionally embedded into the design of the entire programme. Students have multiple meaningful options regarding pace, tracks, delivery modes, progression, and learning pathways.	Flexibility is a core principle of programme design and governance, systematically embedded in all processes.
	Data and evidence	Data is not used. No monitoring of student needs or choice effectiveness.	Data selectively gathered. Flexibility options are primarily informed by professional judgment or past experience.	Decisions about flexible pathways, modes, and pacing are guided by reliable analytics, longitudinal data, demographic insights, and predictive indicators.	Flexibility is continuously monitored, evaluated, and optimised, ensuring it benefits diverse learners without compromising programme coherence.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Courses follow fixed schedules and structures; adjustments are made only in exceptional cases.	Flexibility is available but not coordinated across the whole programme. Students receive some generic guiding regarding flexibility options.	Flexibility options target specific learner groups (working students, international students, resitters). Guidance to make informed choices is available.	Adaptive pathways dynamically adjust based on predictive indicators of progress, risk, and goals. Future needs are anticipated and the programme offers a highly responsive and future-ready flexible structure.
4. Programme load	Design and development	Study load and sequencing are designed course-by-course with no programme coordination.	Programme plans indicative study load, modality distribution, and shared assessment windows.	Structured processes redistribute workload and adjust sequencing across semesters.	Holistic progression of workload and complexity is mapped across the entire programme, aligned with authentic learning trajectories.
	Data and evidence	No tracking of actual workload, clustering, or student time investment.	Survey data are occasionally used to reschedule deadlines.	Study load is monitored using LMS activity, time-on-task data, failed attempts, and drop-out patterns.	Comprehensive workload dashboards support long-term planning using trend and cohort analyses.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Peak workloads remain hidden and unmanaged.	Rules are established to prevent overload (e.g. maximum number of major assessments per week).	Adjustments are made semester-to-semester based on evidence.	Continuous improvement ensures progressive challenge and equitable effort distribution across the full programme.
5. Programme learner guidance	Design and development	No shared expectations for feedback or scaffolding; support varies widely across courses.	Programme-wide feedback standards are introduced (timing, format, workload estimates).	Self-regulated learning (SRL) pathways are explicitly mapped and progressively faded across semesters.	Full SRL curriculum is embedded, including reflection, monitoring, self-assessment, and autonomy development.
	Data and evidence	No monitoring of feedback quality or student workload.	Mid-course surveys track feedback satisfaction and support needs.	LMS analytics monitor time-on-task, assessment returns, and workload spikes.	Real-time alerts and dashboards enable proactive tutor intervention.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Students must navigate support independently.	Tutors respond to general trends and student comments.	Support is tailored by module, semester, and performance patterns.	Personalised early-intervention coaching is triggered by predictive analytics.

Table 12 – continued

Programme dimension	Maturity feature	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
6. Capacity and sustainability	Design and development	Blended teaching practices differ widely between courses; no programme-level guidance or leadership involvement.	Baseline expectations for blended design are defined; coordinators are appointed; core tools and basic PD are provided.	Structured decision-making aligns course models, workload, technology, and support with programme goals.	Long-term blended T&L strategy is co-created by leadership, educators, designers, and technologists, driving sustainable innovation.
	Data and evidence	No programme-level monitoring of blended practices; issues surface only through complaints.	Basic feedback and metrics (e.g. logins, tool satisfaction) are reviewed occasionally.	Systematic collection and analysis of blended teaching and learning data inform redesign and governance decisions.	Integrated data streams (learning analytics, workload, accessibility, PD participation) drive continuous improvement cycles.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Programme reacts only after problems occur; contextual factors (course type, access, skills) are ignored.	Some anticipatory support is provided (e.g. PD sessions, design guidance).	Supports are adapted to different course types and student groups.	Enabling conditions continuously evolve with pedagogical innovation, technological change, and learner diversity.

3.4.5. Dimensions and indicators at organisation level

The organisation level refers to the formal context and organisation where blended education takes place. This is determined by policies and conditions regarding the organization and support of blended T&L.

This is usually a higher education institution such as a university, university of applied sciences, a college of higher education or polytechnic. Depending on the organisational structure, a department such as a faculty, school, or academy may also be considered part of the organisation level. The main stakeholders are the executive board, deans, directors of education, programme directors, department heads, teaching and learning centres, quality and policy officers, and student councils.

The EMBED+Matrix includes the following 8 dimensions across 4 maturity levels:

1. **Strategy and policy:** the extent to which blended teaching and learning are explicitly embedded in the institution's vision, mission, strategic plans, regulations, and formal policies. This dimension focuses on “direction-setting and intent”: defining institutional goals for blended education, ensuring alignment with academic and professional priorities, and providing a coherent policy framework that supports sustainability across faculties and programmes.
2. **Governance and decisionmaking:** the ways in which responsibilities, authority, participation, and accountability for blended teaching and learning are formally organised and enacted within the institution. This includes who makes decisions, how stakeholders (leadership, educators, learners, support staff) are involved, how priorities and trade-offs are negotiated, and how decisions are coordinated across organisational levels.
3. **Support (helps learners & staff do their work now):** the degree to which the institution provides coordinated, accessible, and responsive operational support for blended teaching and learning. This includes pedagogical advice, instructional design consultation, technology assistance, course and programme design support, and helpdesk services that enable educators and students to effectively enact blended practices.
4. **Community building:** the organisation's capacity to foster formal and informal communities of practice that enable collaboration, peer learning, exchange of experiences, co-creation of resources, and collective innovation in blended education across disciplines, roles, and organisational units.
5. **Capacity building (helps staff become more capable over time):** the extent to which the institution develops, sustains, and enhances staff capabilities related to blended teaching and learning. This includes professional development in pedagogy, instructional design, digital literacy, and collaborative course and curriculum development, as well as mentoring, recognition, and career-aligned development pathways that support long-term educational quality.
6. **Technology ecosystem, facilities and digital sovereignty:** the design, management, and stewardship of the institution's digital platforms, educational technologies, and learning spaces to support blended education. This dimension covers interoperability, accessibility, security, scalability, sustainability, and the institution's ability to retain meaningful control over key systems while enabling innovation, analytics, and inclusive learning experiences.

7. **Quality culture:** the extent to which the organisation fosters a culture of monitoring, reflection and continuous quality improvement in blended education. This includes formal QA processes, regular evaluation, data-informed decision-making, integration of metrics for blended approaches, feedback loops, and mechanisms to ensure iterative enhancement of practices across courses, programmes, and the organisation.
8. **Finance and resource allocation:** the degree to which financial and material resources are allocated strategically, transparently, and adaptively to support blended education. This includes investment in infrastructure, professional development, support services, innovation initiatives, and long-term sustainability, as well as mechanisms for prioritisation, evaluation of impact, and adjustment to emerging organisational, faculty and learner needs.

3.4.6. Maturity matrix at organisation level

Table 13

Summary of blended maturity at the organisation level, with examples

Organisation dimension	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
1. Strategy and policy	Blended T&L is absent from organisational vision; initiatives depend on individuals. <i>Example: A department pilots hybrid courses without any reference to organisational priorities.</i>	Organisational goals and policies for blended T&L are articulated and communicated. <i>Example: Strategic plan includes a section on blended education and minimum expectations for programmes.</i>	Strategy is reviewed and refined using structured organisational insights. <i>Example: Programme-level reports inform updates to blended T&L guidelines.</i>	Blended T&L is embedded in mission, strategy, and long-term planning. <i>Example: Blended education is a core pillar in the university's multi-year educational strategy and budget.</i>
2. Governance and decision-making	Responsibilities and authority for blended T&L are unclear or fragmented. <i>Example: Conflicting decisions about tools are made independently by IT, faculties, and central services.</i>	Formal roles and committees for blended education are defined. <i>Example: A steering group with faculty and support representatives oversees blended initiatives.</i>	Governance structures are refined based on participation and effectiveness. <i>Example: Student representatives are added after reviews show limited learner input.</i>	Transparent, inclusive governance enables continuous organisational adaptation. <i>Example: Cross-level governance routinely balances pedagogical, technical, and financial priorities.</i>
3. Support	Support is reactive, fragmented, and focused on technical troubleshooting. <i>Example: Helpdesk only assists with login issues or LMS errors.</i>	Coordinated support services are available for blended teaching. <i>Example: Educators can book consultations with instructional designers.</i>	Support provision is adjusted based on identified needs. <i>Example: Increased support for assessment design after data shows high failure rates.</i>	Proactive, integrated support anticipates needs. <i>Example: Targeted support offered to programmes before large-scale blended redesigns.</i>
4. Community building	Exchange about blended teaching is informal and incidental. <i>Example: Educators occasionally share tips via email or coffee chats.</i>	Recognised communities of practice begin to emerge. <i>Example: Monthly blended teaching lunch sessions are organised.</i>	Communities actively inform organisational learning. <i>Example: Insights from communities feed into organisational design guidelines.</i>	Communities drive innovation and shared ownership. <i>Example: Faculty networks co-create and scale blended course models organisation-wide.</i>
5. Capacity building	Professional development is incidental and optional. <i>Example: One-off workshops organised by enthusiastic individuals.</i>	Structured professional learning opportunities are offered. <i>Example: Annual training programme on blended pedagogy and tools.</i>	Professional learning is aligned with organisational priorities. <i>Example: Targeted training introduced for programmes transitioning to blended formats.</i>	Continuous professional growth embedded in career systems. <i>Example: Blended teaching competence recognised in promotion and appraisal processes</i>
6. Technology ecosystem, facilities and digital sovereignty	Tools and learning spaces are fragmented and inconsistent. <i>Example: Faculties use different, non-integrated video platforms.</i>	Core platforms and facilities are aligned to blended needs. <i>Example: Organisation-wide LMS and hybrid classrooms are standardised.</i>	Ecosystem refined to support diverse practices. <i>Example: Additional tools introduced for lab simulations and collaborative work.</i>	Integrated, future-proof ecosystem enables innovation and inclusion. <i>Example: Interoperable platforms support analytics, accessibility, and personalised learning.</i>

Table 13 – continued

Organisation dimension	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
7. Quality culture	Quality assurance for blended T&L is absent or fragmented. <i>Example: Blended courses are not reviewed differently from traditional ones.</i>	Regular evaluation of blended education is introduced. <i>Example: Student surveys include questions on online-face-to-face coherence.</i>	Evaluation informs systematic improvement. <i>Example: Review findings lead to redesign of assessment practices.</i>	Continuous improvement embedded as shared practice. <i>Example: Ongoing quality dialogues guide innovation across programmes.</i>
8. Finance & resource allocation	Funding for blended T&L is ad hoc and project-based. <i>Example: Short-term grants support isolated pilots.</i>	Dedicated funding streams are established. <i>Example: Central budget covers LMS licenses and staff training.</i>	Resource use reviewed against organisational priorities. <i>Example: Funding reallocated to high-impact blended initiatives.</i>	Long-term, adaptive investment sustains innovation. <i>Example: Multi-year funding supports infrastructure renewal and professional learning cycles.</i>

Table 14*Enactment of blended maturity at the organisation level, per maturity feature*

Organisation Dimension	Maturity feature	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
1. Strategy and policy	Design and development	No explicit institutional vision or strategy for blended T&L; initiatives are fragmented and faculty-driven.	Blended T&L is recognised in strategic documents and policies; initial institutional goals and guidelines are defined.	Organisation-wide blended T&L strategy formalised and operationalised through aligned policies and frameworks.	Fully embedded in institutional mission, strategy, and long-term planning, supporting sustained innovation and coherence.
	Data & evidence	No systematic monitoring or evaluation; decisions rely on anecdotal information.	Basic descriptive data collected and reported; limited influence on policy decisions.	Dashboards and key indicators systematically inform policy refinement and prioritisation.	Continuous and predictive use of longitudinal evidence informs strategic decision-making, scenario planning, and innovation cycles.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Policies uniform and insensitive to faculty, programme, or learner diversity.	Limited flexibility allows for typical contextual differences.	Strategy and policy adapted based on programme-level evidence and faculty contexts.	Governance and policies continuously evolve in response to changing educational, technological, and societal contexts.
2. Governance and decision-making	Design and development	Roles, responsibilities, and authority unclear or informal.	Governance structures exist but operate with limited coordination.	Coordinated governance structures align decision-making across institutional levels.	Transparent, participatory, embedded governance enabling shared ownership and accountability.
	Data and evidence	Decisions reactive, not evidence-informed.	Selected reports or evaluations inform governance discussions.	Evidence systematically informs prioritisation, trade-offs, and coordination decisions.	Predictive and longitudinal data support anticipatory, strategic governance and continuous recalibration.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Decisions vary arbitrarily across units.	Limited accommodation of contextual differences through exceptions.	Governance responsive to disciplinary, organisational, and educational contexts.	Decision-making continuously adapts to emerging needs, innovations, and institutional priorities.
3. Support (operational)	Design and development	Support is fragmented, reactive, and limited in scope.	Centralised support services established, offering basic pedagogical and technical assistance.	Support services coordinated and aligned with institutional priorities, providing multi-level assistance.	Integrated, proactive support ecosystem embedded in institutional processes and workflows.
	Data and evidence	No tracking of support demand or effectiveness.	Basic usage data collected and reviewed periodically.	Evidence from usage and feedback guides improvement and resource allocation.	Predictive analytics anticipate support needs and guide timely interventions.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Support generic, not tailored to roles or disciplines.	Partial adaptation to departmental requests.	Services differentiated by role, experience level, and programme context.	Fully context-aware support dynamically adapts to evolving staff and learner needs.

Table 14 – continued

Organisation Dimension	Maturity feature	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
4. Community building	Design and development	Communities informal, fragmented, weakly recognised.	Initial formal communities and exchange opportunities established.	Communities of practice structurally supported and connected across units.	Community engagement embedded as a driver of innovation, collaboration, and shared ownership.
	Data and evidence	Engagement and impact not monitored.	Participation data and feedback collected occasionally.	Engagement metrics inform community support strategies and capacity development.	Continuous monitoring and predictive insights guide community growth and sustainability.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Communities generic, insensitive to context.	Limited adaptation to departmental or role-specific needs.	Community practices adapted to disciplines, roles, and project contexts.	Communities evolve dynamically with institutional priorities and innovation trajectories.
5. Capacity building	Design and development	Professional learning sporadic, voluntary, weakly linked to institutional goals.	Structured professional development offered, aligned with emerging priorities.	Role-based, programmatic development pathways aligned with strategy.	Continuous, career-aligned professional learning ecosystem supports long-term educational quality.
	Data and evidence	No evaluation of participation, outcomes, or competence.	Feedback and attendance data collected with limited use for planning.	Evidence informs design, targeting, and improvement of development initiatives.	Predictive use of performance and learning data optimises professional development pathways.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Training generic, one-size-fits-all.	Partial differentiation by discipline or role.	Development pathways tailored to educator roles, course types, and organisational needs.	Professional learning dynamically adapts to evolving pedagogical, technological, and institutional contexts.
6. Technology ecosystem, facilities & digital sovereignty	Design and development	Technologies and spaces fragmented, uncoordinated, locally chosen.	Core platforms and facilities standardised, centrally supported.	Ecosystem aligned with pedagogical goals; governance, interoperability, and coordinated planning in place.	Strategically governed, scalable, secure ecosystem supporting analytics, innovation, and institutional autonomy.
	Data and evidence	No systematic insight into technology use or effectiveness.	Basic usage metrics and support data monitored.	Evidence informs optimisation, integration, and adoption decisions.	Continuous, predictive analytics guide innovation, sustainability, and ecosystem evolution.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Accessibility and contextual needs unaddressed.	Limited accommodation of diverse user needs.	Technologies and facilities adapted to course types, learner profiles, and accessibility requirements.	Ecosystem dynamically supports personalisation, inclusiveness, and emerging educational practices.
7. Quality culture	Design and development	QA fragmented; blended T&L not systematically reviewed.	Blended T&L included in QA on ad hoc basis.	Systematic QA cycles integrate blended T&L metrics and governance.	Continuous improvement embedded in institutional culture and routines.
	Data and evidence	Monitoring and evaluation absent or incidental.	Limited data collection informs periodic reviews.	Dashboards and analytics guide targeted quality enhancement.	Predictive, evidence-based QA supports anticipatory improvement and innovation.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	QA processes generic, inflexible.	Partial adaptation to programme or faculty context.	QA mechanisms respond to disciplinary, pedagogical, and organisational variation.	QA continuously adapts to context, strategy, and emerging educational needs.

Table 14 – continued

Organisation Dimension	Maturity feature	Ad hoc	Intentional	Diagnostic	Sustainable
8. Finance and resource allocation	Design and development	Funding fragmented, short-term, inequitable.	Dedicated funding supports core infrastructure and activities.	Strategic allocation aligns resources with blended T&L priorities and impact.	Long-term, adaptive financial planning sustains innovation, inclusiveness, and scalability.
	Data and evidence	No tracking of spending, impact, or ROI.	Basic financial reporting informs oversight.	Evidence on adoption, outcomes, and efficiency guides allocation decisions.	Predictive financial models optimise investment and support strategic foresight.
	Adaptivity and context-awareness	Budgets rigid, poorly responsive to emerging needs.	Limited flexibility accommodates priority initiatives.	Resources reallocated based on organisational data and demand patterns.	Financial systems dynamically respond to institutional priorities, innovation cycles, and contextual change.

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